

ENGLISH IDIOMS, THEIR HISTORY AND USAGE

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ABSTRACT: In this article, we will discuss idioms in English, their history and usage, as idioms are one of the most researched topics in the language. An idiom is a phrase that is common to a certain population. It is typically figurative and usually is not understandable based solely on the words within the phrase. A prior understanding of its usage is usually necessary. Idioms are crucial to the progression of language. They function in a manner that, in many cases, literal meanings cannot.

KEY WORDS: phraseology, phraseologism, phrase, phraseological units, the study of phraseology, idioms, the origin of the idioms.

INTRODUCTION: The main focus of phraseology as a branch of linguistics focuses on studying phraseology. Phraseologism - two or more is a semantically interrelated phrase composed of words. Phraseologism is a lexical unit like a word. They are ready in the language like words. It is not a speech event, but a language event because it exists in this in the article, the study of phraseology, stages of formation and their main features are analyzed. Structure of phraseologisms, lexical-semantic, functional-methodical and syntactic tasks, as well as a language with unique formation features is a unit. Phraseology is a set of stable words specific to a language in linguistics and a section that studies phrases.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: In linguistics, the term phraseology was used by Charles Bally, stylistics combined with science, but the idea of recognizing phraseology as a science famous linguist scientist prof. It is E. F. Polivonov. Slave to this idea another of the scientists who supported him is the famous linguist V. V. Vinogradov. It is in a number of his scientific studies, he taught phraseological combinations in the Russian language collects and semantically divides them into groups. E.D. Polivanov and thoughts on phraseology raised by V. V. Vinogradov later, it prompted the emergence of many studies in this field. But until now, there are opinions about whether or not to consider phraseology as a science did not fully find the solution. Idiom phraseologisms, phraseological combinations and between static phrases (proverbs and proverbs, other

phraseology equivalent to a sentence), according to several differences, some scholars divide phraseology into 2 types: narrow and broad they interpret it in the sense. When it is understood in a broad sense (L.P. Smith, V.P. Zhukov, V.N. Teliya, N.M. Shansky) proverbs and sayings, folk colloquial phrases belonging to his work, a number of forms of speech (greeting, sayings of farewell) are also included.[1.78]

But phraseology is widely used no exaggeration to say that the problem of understanding has not been solved yet it won't happen. Development of phraseology as a special field of linguistics experienced difficult roads. Even the famous English linguist Smirnitsky also supported the fact that phraseology is a separate field of linguistics. - It was a branch of lexicology with the theory of phraseological combinations despite the study of phraseology, it is necessary to study the syntactic part of the language. If we do not recognize phraseology as a separate field, then as a separate science Smirnitsky said in his work "Lexikologia angliškovo yazyka" that we cannot say. [2.134]

When choosing a phraseological equivalent, the translator must have meant it in context should pay attention to the content, otherwise, the selected equivalent is expressed in the text does not correspond to the content, it causes intellectual nonsense. Scientists according to them, in the process of translation, the grammatical tools specific to one language Of course, it is not necessary to give in the second language through grammatical means. In such cases special attention should be paid to the situation or context in the translation. The main thing is in the translation the meaning of phraseological units such as words, emotional - expressive and it is necessary to reflect the formal features while preserving the stylistic features. It is a mistake to study phraseology as a means of disturbing speech and they are highly informative like other language units together with having a feature, a nominative and communicative task in the language are executive units. Phraseologisms are universal language tools, without them language is not available. The stylistic potential of phraseology is very important.

Phraseological stylistics studies the stylistic features of phraseological units and in this field, it relies on the experience of lexical stylistics, the analysis of various stylistic units. After all, it is known that phraseological units perform a nominative function in the language it is characterized by emotionality and expressive features. Language history and etymology are unique in the etymological analysis of phraseological units takes place.[3.82]

1. "Turn a blind eye"

Meaning: To refuse to acknowledge a known truth

Example: I'll turn a blind eye once, but next time you'll be in trouble.

Origin: While many proposed origins of this phrase are disputed, it is commonly accepted that turning a blind eye comes from a comment made by British Admiral Horatio Nelson. In 1801 he led the attack alongside Admiral Sir Hyde Parker in the Battle of Copenhagen. Nelson was blind in one eye. Parker communicated to Nelson at one point, via flags, that he needed to retreat and disengage. Nelson, however, was convinced that he could prevail if they pushed onward. Nelson then, holding the telescope to his blind eye, pretended not to see the signal—making a sly comment to a fellow officer about reserving the right to use his blind eye every now and again.

2. "Feeling under the weather"

Meaning: To feel ill

Example: My son was sick yesterday, and now I'm feeling a bit under the weather.

Origin: This idiom is believed to be nautical in nature. When a sailor was feeling ill, he would go beneath the bow, which is the front part of the boat. This would hopefully protect him from adverse conditions, as he was literally under the bad weather that could further sicken him. Therefore, a sailor who was sick could be described as being "under the weather."

3. "Beat around the bush"

Meaning: To circle the point; to avoid the point

Example: Stop beating around the bush and tell me what really happened.

Origin: This common phrase is thought to have originated in response to game hunting in Britain. While hunting birds, participants would beat bushes in order to draw out the birds. Therefore, they were beating around the bush before getting to the main point of the hunt: actually capturing the birds.

CONCLUSION: The scientific classification of fixed expressions in languages is, first of all, should consist of organizing the terms given to phraseology. In linguistics, there are various terms used to express fixed word combinations is being used. This is the nature of these fixed phrases is occurring due to its complexity. They are semantic, structural and functional are considered complex. Accordingly, phraseologisms are structural-semantic, stylistic, based on semantic, complex, syntactic function in the sentence and other principles classified. Classification based on the structural-semantic principle is recognized as one of the traditional classification methods. According to him, it is a stable word combinations are divided into pairs of words, idioms, wise words

(aphorisms), proverbs. A fixed phrase must consist of at least two words. Couple words consist of units belonging to the same word group phrases with phraseological meaning are counted. The term "idiom" is derived from the Greek means real, original. Idioms are fixed phrases, events, used for expressive description of events and objects, their meaning new, not derived from the sum of the meanings of the constituent components are stable combinations that acquire phraseological meaning. The meaning of some idioms can be expressed by another word, but the connotative meaning in the idiom, stylistic uniqueness is not fully covered by this synonym.

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